

NON-FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE INDICATORS AND LONG-TERM SUVIVAL OF SMALL ENTREPRENEURIAL START-UPS IN AKWA IBOM STATE

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Abstract

Non-financial performance indicators play a crucial role in determining the long-term survival of entrepreneurial businesses by revealing factors influencing their financial performance over time. This study aims to examine the predictive power of these indicators on the longevity of small-scale entrepreneurial startups in Akwa Ibom State. A descriptive survey approach is employed, focusing on 376 small business owners randomly selected from a population of 928 entrepreneurs registered with the Small and Medium Enterprise Development Agency of Nigeria in Akwa Ibom State. Data collection involves a 4-point rating scale questionnaire titled 'Non-financial Performance Measurement Indicators Questionnaire,' validated through a trial test with 30 non-participating small business owners. Researchers and seven trained assistants administered the questionnaire, and statistical analysis, including simple linear regression, was conducted to address research questions and test hypotheses at a significance level of 0.05. The findings indicates that product quality, innovation, and customer satisfaction strongly predict the long-term survival of entrepreneurial startups. Furthermore, these factors are found to have significant predictive power. The study concludes that in today's competitive and uncertain business environment, small-scale entrepreneurs in Akwa Ibom State can enhance their business longevity by prioritising quality, innovation, and customer satisfaction. Recommendations include continual improvement of products to ensure sustained entrepreneurial success.

Introduction

A small entrepreneurial start-up is a novel business that is independently owned and operated, typically not dominant in its industry, yet offers valuable goods or services to customers. These start-ups significantly contribute to any nation's economic development, serving as the backbone of the economy by creating and redistributing wealth, providing employment opportunities, utilising local raw materials, generating government revenue, and supplying goods and services for both households and industries. However, in Akwa Ibom State, many small-scale businesses struggle to survive over the long term. This challenge is one reason why entrepreneurs with new businesses place considerable emphasis on financial performance. Focusing solely on the financial performance of a business does not

provide a complete picture of its overall health; a holistic understanding of performance is necessary. The long-term financial results of a business are merely reflections of various non-financial indicators, such as product quality, timely delivery, customer satisfaction, innovation, benchmarks, and value-for-money (Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria, 2019). Therefore, it is essential to continually assess non-financial performance indicators in entrepreneurial start-ups, as these factors significantly influence profit maximisation and long-term survival.

Assessing non-financial performance measures can enhance a new business's competitiveness by providing crucial insights into its strengths—which entrepreneurs can leverage—and weaknesses that can be minimised or eliminated to ensure survival and long-term success. The non-financial aspects of performance are key determinants of a business's financial performance. Profits can only be achieved when operations are effectively managed. Against this backdrop, this study aims to determine the extent to which non-financial performance measurement indicators predict the long-term survival of small-scale entrepreneurial start-ups in Akwa Ibom State.

Problem Statement/Justification

Entrepreneurs start businesses with the primary objective of generating sufficient profits. This goal often leads to a predominant focus on financial results, such as operating profit and return on investment, while neglecting important non-financial aspects of operations, including product quality, innovation, delivery time, and customer satisfaction. However, the long-term survival of an entrepreneurial start-up relies not only on financial outcomes but also on internal capabilities and future prospects. The operations of small-scale entrepreneurial start-ups are increasingly complex, as much of the information critical to their long-term success cannot be easily quantified in monetary terms. By underestimating the importance of customer satisfaction, many small-scale start-ups may have lost significant numbers of customers to competitors. Additionally, a failure to invest in research and innovation has led these businesses to cede market share to larger firms, resulting in declining profits and, in the worst cases, business closures. Observations indicate that many entrepreneurial start-ups in Akwa Ibom State often cease operations within a few years of establishment. This situation has resulted in significant losses for investors, employee retrenchments, and increased unemployment, all of which contribute to related social issues. It appears that the neglect of non-financial performance measurement indicators may be a significant factor behind the high mortality rate of small-scale entrepreneurial start-ups in Akwa Ibom State. However, assumptions alone cannot be deemed factual; therefore, this study aims to determine the extent to which non-financial performance measurement indicators predict the long-term survival of small-scale entrepreneurial start-ups in Akwa Ibom State.

Objectives of the Research

The main objective of the study is to determine the extent to which non-financial performance measurement indicators predict the long-term survival of small-scale entrepreneurial start-ups in Akwa Ibom State. In specific terms, the study sought to determine the extent to which;

1. Product quality predicts the long-term survival of small-scale entrepreneurial start-ups.
2. Innovation predicts the long-term survival of small-scale entrepreneurial start-ups.
3. Customer satisfaction predicts the long-term survival of small-scale entrepreneurial start-ups.

Research Questions

1. The following research questions guided the study.
2. What is the extent to which product quality predicts the long-term survival of small-scale entrepreneurial start-ups?
3. What is the extent to which innovation predicts the long-term survival of small-scale entrepreneurial start-ups?
4. What is the extent to which customer satisfaction predicts the long-term survival of small-scale entrepreneurial start-ups?

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at the 0.05 level of significance.

1. Product quality does not significantly predict the long-term survival of small-scale entrepreneurial start-ups.
2. Innovation does not significantly predict the long-term survival of small-scale entrepreneurial start-ups.
3. Customer satisfaction does not significantly predict the long-term survival of small-scale entrepreneurial start-ups.

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Non-financial performance measurements are essential for any entrepreneurial business. Non-financial performance encompasses all aspects of business operations that are not financial in nature (Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria, 2021). These measurement indicators are quantitative metrics that cannot be expressed in monetary terms. According to Vision Edge (2021), non-financial measures include customer satisfaction, innovation, delivery time, corporate social responsibility, market share, and benchmarking. These indicators serve as leading indicators of future financial performance, providing valuable insights into business operations.

Nonfinancial measures help entrepreneurs understand the underlying reasons for certain financial outcomes and identify actions needed to improve their start-up's financial results.

Product quality is a critical component of business success. Donald, Dobler, David, and Burt, as cited in Udukeke (2024), define quality as the attribute and degree of excellence associated with a particular purpose. It encompasses the complete set of features and characteristics of goods or services that satisfy specific needs. Key dimensions of product quality include durability, performance, reliability, usability, serviceability, and conformance. For a start-up to attract a significant customer base, it must offer products of superior quality compared to its competitors. Establishing quality standards is critical because they define the criteria for product design and production. Addressing quality issues entails both direct costs (e.g., replacing items and shipping) and indirect costs (e.g., lost goodwill leading to future sales declines) (Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria, 2019).

Namara (2014) investigated the effect of product quality on organisational performance within the beverage industry in Uganda, specifically focusing on Nile Breweries Limited. The findings revealed that perceived quality positively impacts organisational performance, with a significant correlation of 0.622. Additionally, reliability positively influenced organisational performance, confirmed at 0.657, and there was a strong relationship between responsiveness and organisational performance, with a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.762. Yuliansyah and Razimi (2015) conducted research on non-financial performance measures and managerial performance, highlighting the mediating role of innovation in an Indonesian stock exchange-listed organization. Their findings showed that non-financial performance measures have a positive impact on individual performance, which is fully mediated by innovation. This suggests that managers should prioritise non-financial performance measures to enhance innovation and improve individual performance. Emeakponuzo (2014) examined the relationship between non-financial performance measures and firm value in Nigeria from 2006 to 2010. The study found that non-financial performance indicators—such as new product development, market position strength, and quality of investor communication—positively impact the value of firms in Nigeria.

In this context, innovation refers to the process of implementing creative ideas within a business. The term is derived from the Latin word *innovare*, meaning "to make something new." Innovation encompasses new ideas, devices, or methods and is often viewed as the application of better solutions that address new requirements, unarticulated needs, or existing market demands. Saedah (2002), as cited in John-Africa (2016), defines innovation as the implementation of a new or significantly improved product (goods and services) through more effective products, processes, services, technologies, or business models that are not readily available in the market, government, or society. It can also be described as "something original and

more effective that breaks into the market or society" (Wikipedia, n.d.). Ultimately, innovation is the process of turning new ideas into practical reality. Luecke and Katz (2003) explain that creativity serves as the foundation for innovation. For innovation to occur, there must be a creative idea and the capability to convert that idea into actionable outcomes that create a difference. Innovation, therefore, is the successful implementation of creative ideas and the utilisation of new concepts. In simple terms, innovation involves exploiting new ideas. The key definitions surrounding innovation highlight that it is often perceived as occurring primarily in high-tech environments.

(Gunday, Ulusoy, Kilic, & Alpkam, 2011). Innovativeness is a critical component of growth strategies, enabling businesses to enter new markets, increase market share, and achieve sustained profitability. Beyond profitability, innovation fosters more efficient manufacturing practices, enhances market performance, and helps maintain a positive perception among customers. Innovations provide firms with a strategic pathway to navigate challenges and achieve a sustainable competitive edge. Moreover, innovation creates something new that holds significant value for individuals, groups, organisations, industries, or the public (Altman, Nagle, & Tushman, 2014). Currently, innovation is key to gaining a competitive advantage in any new business. It helps organisations address various challenges, not just competition. Rapid changes, globalisation, advancing technology, and the shift from an industrial to a knowledge-based economy all necessitate innovative solutions. By leveraging insights from relevant literature, a firm can avoid stagnation and instead achieve a competitive advantage (Halkos & Bousinakis, 2012). Additionally, in a turbulent environment, innovation is essential for maintaining competitive advantage and serves as a driving force for economic growth at the national level. The capacity to innovate is often linked to the ability to compete effectively at individual, firm, regional, and national levels. The value created by innovations frequently manifests in new methods, products, and processes that contribute to wealth (Ballot, Fakhfakh, Galia, & Salter, 2015). When viewing a firm as a collection of resources, capabilities, and competencies, the impact of innovation is to enhance the organisation's internal capabilities, making it more adaptable and better equipped to learn and exploit new ideas (Gemmill, 2011). Management practices also encompass innovation. Managerial innovations, such as new organisational structures and processes, can add value to a corporation (Hamel, 2006). Although management-related innovations are not the sole contributors to successful innovation, human capital remains a crucial factor (Tuan, Nhan, Giang, & Ngoc, 2016). Ultimately, effective management can foster innovation within large-scale organisations, creating lasting advantages and enhancing competitiveness (Cheng, Yang, & Sheu, 2014).

In this view, creativity is the starting point of innovation; the first is a necessity but not a sufficient condition for the second to occur. According to Usip and Ukoima (2023), innovation provides the following benefits:

1. It allows businesses to expand their customer base by refreshing the market with new and improved products. businesses can expand their customer base.
2. It is a critical component of competitive advantage and helps companies stay ahead of their competitors.
3. It supports the ability to charge at a premium.
4. It generates incremental revenue and increases shareholder value.
5. It establishes a positive reputation for an organisation.

In Nigeria, Nwanji et al. (2017) investigated the effectiveness of non-financial performance measures on managerial performance in agro-allied industries. The findings indicate a significant relationship between non-financial performance measures and managerial performance in these industries. Additionally, the study found that non-financial performance enables organisations to meet the needs and interests of their wider stakeholders.

Tuan et al. (2016) explored two aspects: the impacts of innovation on various facets of innovation performance and their effects on firm performance, including production, market, and financial performance. The results showed that process, marketing, and organisational innovations had a positive impact on firm performance. Specifically, a higher level of innovative activities correlates with greater innovative performance, indicating that increased process, organisational, and marketing innovation activities lead to improved innovative performance. Furthermore, higher levels of process, organisational, and marketing innovation performance are linked to better overall firm performance. To enhance innovation and firm performance, firms in supporting industries should prioritise process, marketing, and organisational innovation activities over product innovation. Because a business's existence is dependent on its customers, suppliers have a vested interest in retaining and expanding their customer base. If supplier companies can retain existing customers or acquire new ones, it will lead to growth in various forms (Aswad, 2012). Customer satisfaction depends not only on the quality, characteristics, and performance of services, but also on consumer expectations. In today's market, the volume of supply often exceeds effective demand, resulting in intense competition among companies striving to meet similar customer needs. To enhance competitiveness, companies must focus on meeting specific customer requirements. However, many companies lack sufficient knowledge about their clients (Morauszki, Lajos, & Menyhárt, 2015).

Customer satisfaction is defined by Westbrook and Reilly (1981) as an emotional response to the experiences associated with specific products or services, retail outlets, or broader behavioural patterns, as well as the overall marketplace. Hunt (2017) further elaborates that customer satisfaction is the evaluation of the service rendered, ensuring that the experience meets or exceeds expectations. Tse and Wilton (2018) expand on Hunt's definition, stating that customer satisfaction involves the

consumer's response to the perceived discrepancy between prior expectations and the actual performance of a product following its consumption. Satisfaction is thus defined as the customer's fulfilment response—a judgement indicating that a product or service feature, or the product or service itself, provides a pleasurable level of consumption-related fulfilment (Oliver, 1977). This definition encompasses two perspectives: the first defines satisfaction as a final state resulting from the consumption experience, while the second emphasises the perceptual, evaluative, and psychological processes that contribute to satisfaction (Evangelos and Yannis, 2010). In modern business philosophy, organisations should be customer-oriented, and the principles of continuous improvement underscore the importance of evaluating and analysing customer satisfaction.

In essence, customer satisfaction serves as a benchmark for standardisation and excellence in performance for many businesses. It also aids in identifying potential market opportunities (Evangelos and Yannis, 2010). Highlighting the importance of customer satisfaction from a business perspective, Zairi (2010) asserts that customers are the core purpose of business activities; rather than businesses depending on customers, they are fundamentally reliant on them. The customer should not be seen as a source of problems, and businesses should not wish for customers to “go away,” as their future and security depend on customer loyalty. The concept of customer satisfaction is not new; it gained prominence in the early 1980s when researchers identified it as a critical indicator of customer loyalty (Oliver, 1997). Oliver also found that customer satisfaction directly correlates with company profitability, return on investment (ROI), and market share. Satisfied customers are less likely to switch to alternatives, as they develop emotional attachments and have concerns about the quality of alternatives. Zairi (2010) emphasises the importance of customer satisfaction by noting two key points: first, satisfied customers share their positive experiences with an average of five or six people, while dissatisfied customers typically inform ten people about their negative experiences. Second, many customers do not voice their dissatisfaction, which companies must recognise because it varies across different industries. Measuring customer satisfaction has become an important issue for most business organisations today.

In recent decades, the significance of customer satisfaction has grown, leading many organisations to establish it as a key parameter for assessment. It is considered a reliable source of feedback, providing an effective, direct, meaningful, and objective understanding of customer preferences and expectations (Gerson, 2013). Hill (2016) asserts that measuring customer satisfaction fosters a sense of achievement and accomplishment among all employees involved in the customer service process, motivating them to perform better and achieve higher productivity levels. Evangelos and Yannis (2005) emphasise that measuring customer satisfaction helps businesses evaluate their current position against competitors and design appropriate plans

accordingly. Additionally, satisfaction measurement can identify potential market opportunities and aid in understanding customer behaviour, particularly by analysing customer expectations, needs, and desires. Customer satisfaction is a critical concern for all types of business organisations. Companies strive to provide the best service while seeking ways to increase customer satisfaction levels. According to Hokinson (2015), key factors influencing customer satisfaction include friendly and knowledgeable employees, helpful service, accurate and timely billing, competitive pricing, service quality, excellent value, billing clarity, and prompt service. Furthermore, Ahmada and Zabri (2016) found a positive relationship between customer satisfaction and business performance and productivity.

Theoretical Framework

Kaplan and Norton (1996) developed the Balanced Scorecard (BSC) as a comprehensive framework for assessing business performance. This model incorporates both financial and non-financial measures, supplementing traditional financial metrics with non-financial indicators across various perspectives, including customer satisfaction, internal business processes, and innovation. For each perspective, Kaplan and Norton stresses that organisations should identify key performance measures and targets.

The Balanced Scorecard comprises four perspectives:

- 1. Financial Perspective:** This includes traditional financial measures such as revenue growth, return on investment (ROI), return on assets (ROA), market share, and earnings per share (EPS).
- 2. Customer Perspective:** This focuses on measures important to customers, such as timeliness, quality, performance, cost, and service.
- 3. Internal Business Process Perspective:** This evaluates the critical internal activities and processes the organization uses to meet customer expectations.
- 4. Learning and Growth Perspective:** This assesses the organization's ability to adapt and innovate for the future, encompassing factors such as time to market for new product development, workforce training and development, and process improvement.

These perspectives provide a multi-dimensional balance between internal and external viewpoints, leading and lagging indicators, objective and subjective measures, and current versus future needs. Trade-offs become explicit business decisions guided by strategy, as illustrated below.

Adapted from Kaplan and Norton

Figure 2.1: Perspectives of Balance Score Card

Each measure for each perspective in a balanced scorecard is selected based on the corporate vision and strategy. For each measure, there is a defined goal, a target, and specific initiatives to translate the goal into action. Cause and effect relationships among the measures explicitly define how the various elements contribute to achieving strategic goals. This becomes a communication mechanism to demonstrate the meaning of the strategy and how different perspectives and departments contribute to achieving the strategy (Velnampy and Nimalathasan, 2007). The relevance of this framework to the proposed study is that the framework focused majorly on non-financial metrics which are the cross of this study.

Research Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey design and was conducted in Akwa Ibom State. In the region, the population consisted of 928 small-scale entrepreneurs registered with the Small and Medium Scale Enterprise Development Agency of Nigeria. A sample of 376 entrepreneurs was selected using a simple random sampling technique.

Data was collected through a 4-point rating scale questionnaire titled '**Non-Financial Performance Measurement Indicators Questionnaire.**' This instrument was developed by the researcher based on the guiding research questions and insights from the reviewed literature. To ensure validity, the questionnaire underwent face and content validation by three experts in business education. Additionally, a pilot test was conducted with 30 entrepreneurs not involved in the actual study. The researcher administered the questionnaire with the assistance of seven trained research assistants who were briefed on the procedures. Completed

questionnaires were collected from the respondents. Simple linear correlation analysis was employed to address the three research questions and to test the three null hypotheses at a significance level of 0.05. The R-value and the associated nature of the relationship, as outlined by Joshua (2005), were used as guidelines for interpreting the results and making decisions regarding the research questions.

Interpretation of r-value relationship of the variables

Coefficient (r)	Relationship
$\pm .00$ to $\pm .19$	Negligible, very low, little or none (very weak relationship)
$\pm .20$ to $\pm .39$	Present, slight, but low (weak relationship)
$\pm .40$ to $\pm .59$	Average, moderate, fairly high (moderate relationship)
$\pm .60$ to $\pm .69$	High (strong relationship)
$\pm .70$ to ± 1.00	Very high (very strong relationship)
- 1	Perfect negative relationship
0	No relationship
+1	Perfect positive relationship

In order to test the null hypotheses, the calculated P-value was compared with the table value. When the calculated P-value is less than the alpha level, the null hypotheses (H_0) were rejected in favour of the alternative hypotheses. But if the calculated P-value is greater than the P-value, the null hypothesis was upheld.

Results

Research Question 1

1. What is the extent to which product quality predicts the long-term survival of small-scale entrepreneurial start-ups?

Table 1: The result of simple linear regression analysis of the extent to which product quality predict the long-term survival of small-scale entrepreneurial start-ups

Variables	R	R ²	% Extent of Contribution	Adjusted R ²	Remark
Product Quality	.610	.372			High Extent
Long-Term Survival					

The result in Table 1 indicated the values of calculated R (strength of prediction) and R² (coefficient of determination of the extent of prediction) between product quality and long-term survival of entrepreneurial start-ups. In Akwa Ibom State, an R-value of 0.61 indicated that product quality predicted the long-term survival of

entrepreneurial start-ups to a high degree. The R^2 -value of .372 shows that 37.2 percent of entrepreneurial start-ups long-term survival is contributed by product quality.

Research Question 2

1. What is the extent to which innovation predicts the long-term survival of small-scale entrepreneurial start-ups?

Table 2: The result of simple linear regression analysis of the extent to which innovation predicts the long-term survival of small-scale entrepreneurial start-ups

Variables	R	R ²	% Extent of Contribution	Adjusted R	Remark
Innovation	.608	.369			High Extent
Long-Term Survival					

The result in Table 1 indicated the values of calculated R (strength of prediction) and R^2 (coefficient of determination of the extent of prediction) between innovation and long-term survival of entrepreneurial start-ups. The R-value of 0.608 indicated that innovation predicted the long-term survival of entrepreneurial start-ups in Akwa Ibom State to a high extent. The R^2 value of .369 shows that 36.9 percent of entrepreneurial start-ups long-term survival is contributed by innovation.

Research Question 3

1. What is the extent to which customer satisfaction predicts the long-term survival of small-scale entrepreneurial start-ups?

Table 3: The result of simple linear regression analysis of the extent to which product quality predicts the long-term survival of small-scale entrepreneurial start-ups

Variables	R	R ²	% Extent of Contribution	Adjusted R ²	Remark
Innovation	.540	.292			High Extent
Long-Term Survival					

The result in Table 3 indicated the values of calculated R (strength of prediction) and R^2 (coefficient of determination of the extent of prediction) between product quality and long-term survival. The R-value of 0.540 indicated that customer satisfaction

predicted the long-term survival of entrepreneurial start-ups in Akwa Ibom State to a high degree. The R^2 value of .292 shows that 29 percent of entrepreneurial start-ups long-term survival is contributed by customer satisfaction.

Null Hypotheses

Null Hypothesis 1

Product quality does not significantly predict the long-term survival of small-scale entrepreneurial start-ups.

Table 4: Regression analysis of product quality on long-term survival of small entrepreneurial start-ups

Model	Sources of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P<0.05
1	Regression	44376.712	1	44376.712	216.54	.000
	Residual	75007.344	366	204.938		
	Total	119384.056	367			

a. Dependent Variable: Long-Term Survival

b. Predictors: (Constant), Product Quality

As shown in Table 4, the calculated probability value of .000 is less than the declared probability value (Alpha level) .05. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that product quality significantly predicts long-term survival of small-scale entrepreneurial start-ups.

Null Hypothesis 2

Innovation does not significantly predict long-term survival of small-scale entrepreneurial start-ups.

Table 5: Regression analysis of product quality on long-term survival of small entrepreneurial start-ups

Model	Sources of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P<0.05
1	Regression	44071.100	1	44071.100	214.173	.000
	Residual	75312.955	366	205.773		
	Total	119384.056	367			

a. Dependent Variable: Long-Term Survival

b. Predictors: (Constant), Innovation

As shown in Table 5, the calculated probability value of .000 is less than the declared probability value (Alpha level) of .05. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. This

implies that innovation significantly predicts the long-term survival of small-scale entrepreneurial start-ups.

Null Hypothesis 3

Customer satisfaction does not significantly predict the long-term survival of small-scale entrepreneurial start-ups.

Table 6: Regression analysis of product quality on long-term survival of small entrepreneurial start-ups

Model	Sources of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P<0.05
1	Regression	43606.524	1	43606.524	210.616	.000
	Residual	75777.532	366	207.042		
	Total	119384.056	367			

a. Dependent Variable: Long-Term Survival

b. Predictors: (Constant), Customer Satisfaction

As shown in Table 6, the calculated probability value of .000 is less than the declared probability value (Alpha level) of .05. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that customer satisfaction significantly predicts the long-term survival of small-scale entrepreneurial start-ups.

Discussion of Findings

The study's findings are summarised below.

The results from research question one indicate that product quality predicts the long-term survival of entrepreneurial start-ups in Akwa Ibom State. This aligns with Emeakponuzo (2010), who found that non-financial performance measurements, such as new product development, market position strength, and quality of investor communication, positively impact firm value. The product development process can enhance the quality of a firm's offerings. Product quality refers to a product's ability to perform its intended functions, such as durability, reliability, accuracy, ease of operation, and repair, among other valuable attributes. Quality is often defined as fitness for use, referring to the extent to which a product meets consumer needs. To acquire and retain a substantial customer base, businesses must provide superior product quality. By focusing on improving product quality, entrepreneurial startups can better satisfy their customers. Additionally, the findings from hypothesis one demonstrate that product quality significantly predicts the long-term survival of small-scale entrepreneurial start-ups. This finding is consistent with Namara (2014), who found that perceived quality positively affects an organisation's performance. When an entrepreneur's product meets customer quality expectations, it increases the likelihood of repeat business, thereby helping the business generate sufficient

revenue to meet its obligations. The findings from research question two indicate that product innovation significantly predicts the long-term survival of entrepreneurial start-ups in Akwa Ibom State. This result aligns with Tuan et al. (2016), who identified positive effects of process, marketing, and organisational innovations on firm performance. Specifically, the research indicates that a higher level of innovation activities leads to greater innovative performance. This means that increased levels of process, organisational, and marketing innovation activities correspond to higher innovative performance. Innovation entails introducing something new into the business. This can involve improving or replacing business processes to enhance efficiency and productivity, as well as expanding the range or quality of existing products or services.

Additionally, it includes developing entirely new and improved goods and services to meet rapidly changing consumer demands, thereby adding value to existing offerings and differentiating the business from competitors. The successful implementation of new ideas is crucial for businesses to improve their processes, launch new and enhanced products, increase efficiency, and ultimately boost profitability. Markets—whether local, regional, national, or global—are becoming increasingly competitive due to greater access to new technologies and enhanced trading and knowledge-sharing opportunities provided by the Internet. Introducing innovation can help entrepreneurial businesses achieve several key objectives: improving productivity, reducing costs, enhancing competitiveness, building brand value, establishing new partnerships, increasing turnover, and improving profitability. Conversely, businesses that fail to innovate risk losing market share to competitors, declining productivity and efficiency, losing key staff, experiencing reduced profit margins, and ultimately facing financial failure.

Furthermore, the findings from hypothesis two reveal that innovation significantly predicts the long-term survival of small-scale entrepreneurial start-ups. This finding is consistent with Nwanji et al. (2017), who found a meaningful positive relationship between non-financial performance measures and managerial performance in agro-allied industries. Additionally, non-financial performance enables organisations to meet the needs and interests of a broader range of stakeholders. When the needs of customers and other stakeholders are consistently addressed, the long-term survival of the entrepreneurial business is more assured.

The findings from research question three indicate that customer satisfaction significantly predicts the long-term survival of entrepreneurial start-ups in Akwa Ibom State. This aligns with the research conducted by Ahmada and Zabri (2016), who found a positive relationship between customer satisfaction and business performance and productivity. Customer satisfaction is a crucial factor that helps organisations differentiate themselves from competitors. It measures how well a

company's products and services meet or exceed customer expectations. Customer satisfaction is defined as the number or percentage of customers whose reported experiences with a firm, its products, or its services exceed specified satisfaction goals. It serves as a key performance indicator in business and is often included in a balanced scorecard. In a competitive marketplace where companies vie for customers, customer satisfaction is regarded as a vital differentiator and has increasingly become a core element of business strategy. Organisations that prioritise customer satisfaction are likely to perform better than their peers in the same industry. Effective customer satisfaction measurement should exhibit high reliability and low error variances. Additionally, the findings from Hypothesis 3 demonstrate that customer satisfaction significantly predicts the long-term survival of small-scale entrepreneurial start-ups. This is consistent with the insights of Evangelos and Yannis (2005), who emphasised that measuring customer satisfaction enables businesses to assess their current position relative to competitors and design appropriate strategies accordingly. When customers are satisfied, they are more likely to remain loyal and continue supporting a particular organisation. Entrepreneurial start-ups can leverage customer satisfaction to gain a competitive advantage and capture a larger market share.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it can be concluded that, to ensure the long-term survival of entrepreneurial start-ups in today's highly competitive and uncertain business environment, small-scale entrepreneurs must prioritise quality, innovation, and customer satisfaction to foster business growth. Unfortunately, many small-scale entrepreneurial ventures often neglect to seek ways to enhance their products and improve customer satisfaction, instead relying on divine intervention and luck for their survival.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Small-scale entrepreneurs should continuously explore ways to enhance their products. This will help them attract new customers and retain existing ones, promoting long-term growth and survival.
2. Small-scale entrepreneurs should generate innovative ideas that can lead to the development of new products. This approach will enable them to meet evolving market needs effectively.
3. Small-scale entrepreneurs should consistently seek novel methods to satisfy their customers, fostering loyalty and ensuring their long-term survival.

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A declaration of competing interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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